

Pupil Teachers' Perception about School Internship : Issues & Challenges

Reena Uniyal Tiwari

Associate Professor, Department of Teacher Education
D.A.V. (P.G.) College, Dehradun Email: drreenatiwari@gmail.com

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Abstract

The teacher is the heart of the school system. For quality education to children, formal education system needs qualified and professional responsible teachers. To prepare professional teachers, Teacher Education program is the means. During B.Ed Program practice teaching of B.Ed students in real classroom conditions is an integral part. Prospective teachers need to undergo School Internship for quality enhancement. The present study aims to examine the perception of B.Ed students towards teaching practice experience (school internship). A research methods approach using google form questionnaire to gather the experiences related to practice teaching and challenges faced during school internship program was carried out to 300 second year (fourth semester) B.Ed students from various B.Ed colleges of Uttarakhand State. The findings indicate that the students teachers had a strong positive perception about school internship as an important part of B.Ed program, where they learn to teach by experiential learning in real classroom situations. The student internship program also prepared them for the real world of school education. The results further revealed that about 70% pupil teachers agreed that the school internship program was an enriching experience. The main challenges faced were- Lack of resources and material and planning and preparation of lesson plan. The present paper discusses in detail the findings and recommendations for school internship to make it an effective experience.

Keywords: B.Ed Program, School Internship, Teaching Practice, Microteaching Skills, Prospective Teachers, Perception, Experience, Challenges

Introduction

"Education is not the preparation of life: Education is life itself."

- John Dewey

Education plays a very important role in human's life. It is the basic human right and it is the process to teach people to learn right. To make education more meaningful, teachers with knowledge, skills and ability to do professional duties and responsibilities are essential. Teachers can be agents of change in any society and they are the heart of any school system. In the present world with constant changes and challenges, teachers need to be provided with right and varied range of knowledge, skills, attitude, thought process and relevant qualification and experience. Teaching is one of the most common profession in our Indian society. In Uttarakhand state, it is the most inspiring and complete profession. In Indian context, Bachelor of Education is two years pre-service teacher education program in which during first year (II semester) B.Ed students go to school for teaching practice (10 days). During the second year (III semester) of B.Ed program, school internship for three months is one of the most important components in the preparations of pre-service teachers.

School Internship:

In Uttarakhand state, B.Ed program/colleges are affiliated either to a central university - Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University, Uttarakhand or two state universities - Sri Dev Suman University, Tehri or Kumaun University, Almora.

The practical component of B.Ed program includes school internship for 14 weeks in real class-room settings.

Students apply for internships through permission letters from their respective B.Ed colleges. In the practising school the B.Ed students teaching in classroom is observed by mentor teachers of school subjects in the practising school. Along with teaching of minimum 45 lesson in each pedagogy subject student teachers also must

- Give final criticism lesson in both teaching subjects
- Work on classroom-based research projects
- Maintain a teacher portfolio
- Two-week work in a society/NGO

Statement of Problem

This study investigates the perception of B.Ed students towards school internship. It also highlights those issues and challenges that pupil teachers (B.Ed students) confront while delivering the content in classes and other routine school activities. During internship, student teachers focus more on completing the lecture and the teaching skills in developing effective lesson plan and delivery are ignored. The teacher educators from B.Ed colleges do not observe the classroom teaching of B.Ed students regularly. There is also lack of assessment for measuring the performance of B.Ed students in the practising schools. The mentor teachers from school are not in a position to provide regular and constructive feedback to B.Ed students.

Consequently, all are B.Ed colleges are unable to achieve the objective of school internship and student teachers fail to implement learned teaching strategies in real classroom situations.

Research Questions:

- Perception of Pupil teachers about school Internship.
- Do all B.Ed students perceive the teaching practice the teaching practice during school internships effective and practicable.
- Are there any gaps in the B.Ed training program which affect the pupil teachers' class room performance.
- What are the issues and challenges faced by pupil teachers during school internship.

Scope of Study:

The study is delimited to Govt. aided and self-finance colleges of Dehradun affiliated to H.N.B Garhwal Control University Srinagar and ShridevSuman State University , Tehri. It is also restricted in that resources and access to data is limited to participants who have just completed their school internship in the month of April 2023 and their size limits its generalization.

This study will serve as the valuable source to understand the perception of pupil teachers about the school internship. It will also help the curriculum developers and teacher education design an effective and practical, school internships program and strengthen the nature of existing B.Ed program.

Review of Literature

Stones& Morris (1972) emphasize the teaching practice as integr part of the teaching practice as integral part of the teaching profession as it develops the teachers; knowledge structure, instructional framework. They also claim that assessment of practice teaching for certification is very challenging Good(1983) elaborates that teaching practice components help to createan effective and reliable teacher. Lyle(1996) & Stone(1987) stressed that supervision during teaching practice facilitates student-teachers' professional learning by brigding the gap between theory and practice. Wood(1989) commented that teachers' competency may be increased through a professional plan to maximise their potential abilities in an encouraging teaching environment. Researches by (Koehler 1988; Sabar, 2004; Korthagen, etal; 2006) described teaching practice to have either negative or positive attributes developed among student teachers. Further studies by (Edmunds on 1990, Tang, 2003; Tickle, 2000, Wilson, 2006) advocated that teaching practice often failed to achieve the described pedagogic outcomes despite the long time spent on teaching practice.

Qazi, Rawat, Sharjeel, 2008 mentioned that B.Ed practice teaching does not exchange teacher's real classroom skills. Practicing schools & B.Ed colleges do not provide sufficient support to increase effectiveness.

Research Tools :

Survey research design was used. Data was collected through google questionnaire form in order to know the perception of pupil teachers about the effectiveness of various dimensions of school internship to find about their views and challenges faced by them.

Target Population:

Two government aided B.Ed colleges and four self finance B.Ed colleges of Dehradun city comprised the population of the study. All B.Ed students/pupil teachers who had completed the school internship in the months from January to April 2023 were the population of this study.

Sampling:

The study employed a simple random sample of 255 student teachers. The participants of the study had completed their B.Ed school internship in Jan-April 2023. All participants were between the age group of 20-40 years.

Research Instrument:

The perception of student teachers were collected through google form questionnaire containing 20 questions related to school internship. The responses were collected on a five point scale from student teachers with a response options- strongly disagree, disagree, undecided, agree and strongly agree.

Data Analysis:

Descriptive and simple percentage calculation techniques were used for analysing.

1). Age-

Out of 225 pupil teachers who responded only 247 disclosed their age. The respondents n=255 participants were in the group age 20 to 30 years. Maximum 150 pupil teachers were in the age of 23 to 25 years.

2) Gender-

Out of 225 pupil teachers who responded, only 248 revealed their gender. Out of which there were 80.6% female pupil teachers and 19.4% male pupil teachers.

- 3) Type of B.Ed College-
68% pupil teachers were from private/self finance B.Ed college and 32% from government aided B.Ed colleges.

- 4) Type of Practising School-
62.8% pupil teachers completed their school internship from government schools. Whereas only 37.2% pupil teachers opted for private schools to undergo their internship.

- 5) Duration of School Internship-
Out of 249 responses received more than half 51.8% pupil teachers had done school internship for 3 months 43% for 4 months, but there was a small number pupil teachers 4% who had done school internship for one month only.

- 6) 45% Pupil teachers strongly agreed and 52.6% agreed that the school internship program provided opportunities to improve teaching skills. Less than 3% of pupil teachers either disagreed or were indecisive about the opportunity provided for improvement in teaching skills through School Internship Program.

- 7) Whether the microteaching skills practiced in B.Ed college helped in school teaching, 35.7% pupil teachers strongly agreed, 61% agreed. Less than 4% pupil teachers were not sure about it.

- 8) When asked about the lesson plan preparation taught in B.Ed college and implementation in planning the teaching in real classroom situations. About 7% pupil teachers either were undecided, disagreed or strongly disagreed. However 32.9% strongly agreed and 61% agreed to it.

- 9) 94.3% pupil teachers agreed that mentor teacher from practising school supervised their teaching. Only 5.7% pupil teachers said no to it.

- 10) 32.1% pupil teachers strongly agreed and 66.3% agreed that the school internship program helped in improving their class room management skills. Only less than 2% pupil teachers disagreed to it.

- 12) Around 6.3% pupil teachers were either indecisive or disagreed, that mentor teacher provided proper feedback for teaching skills whereas 19.4% strongly agreed and 73.3% agreed to it.

- 13) To handle diverse students in classroom, B.Ed classes were helpful according to 95.5% of pupil teachers, less than 5% disagreed to it.

- 14) 35.55 pupil strongly agreed and 63.5% agreed that the school internship experience helped them to develop new teaching strategies. Very few less than 1% disagreed.

- 15) 70.6% pupil teachers agreed and 26.6% strongly agreed that they were able to use different teaching methods during school internship. Whereas less than 3% disagreed.

16) Pupil teachers responses to opportunities provided by school internship were as follows.

- A) Conducting morning assembly- 70.39%
- B) Maintenance of Registers- 51.8%
- C) Time table preparation- 42.2%
- D) Evaluation of students work- 29.7%
- E) Conducting PTM- 29.7%
- F) Conducting Co-curricular activities- 76.7%

17) During the school internship following challenges were faced by pupil teachers.

- A) 40% Pupil teachers faced the lack of resources and materials during school internship.
- b) 30% pupil teachers faced the challenge in planning and preparation of lesson.
- c) No opportunity to participate in schools, other activities was the challenge for 18.12% pupil teacher
- d) 17.2% pupil teachers had the challenge of negative attitude of school students.
- e) 13.2% pupil teacher were of the opinion that inappropriate time of internship was a challenge.
- f) 12.3% pupil teachers faced the challenge of inadequate supervision.
- g) No relation between theory and practice was a challenge for 11.9% pupil teachers.
- h) For 11% of pupil teachers, the duration of school internship was less.
- i) 10.6% pupil teachers faced the challenge of mismatch between time of school internship and school calender.
- j) 3.1% pupil teachers had the negative attitude of the school principal/teachers as a challenge.

18) 29% pupil teachers strongly agreed and 68.5% agreed that the school internship program was enriching and wholesome experience.

Discussion:

The existing School Internship in B.Ed two years course is presently focussed on the scholastic and skill expertise of pupil teachers. The theory taught in B.Ed classes lack latest knowledge and assessment procedure as well as innovative pedagogic concepts . Most of the lesson delivery in school internship relies on textual contexts and lecturing is still considered to be most followed method. Prior preparation of pupil teachers for school internship is not done in appropriate and effective manner. Only 50% of the pupil teachers responded that they received appropriate opportunities during school internship to

learn the various responsibilities of a teacher other than class room teaching. Challenges faced by pupil teachers during school internship were basically-

The lack of resources and materials, problem in planning and preparation of lesson plans, less opportunities to participate in other school activities, etc.

Recommendations:

1. Before the start of school internship program, its objectives should be discussed and decided with pupil teachers (B.Ed students), school teachers (mentor teacher) and school principals.
2. The duration of school internship to be increased and in accordance with the school academic calendar, so that pupil teachers can have fruitful learning experience.
3. B.Ed supervisors and school's mentor teachers to be oriented to critically play their role in giving proper feedback to pupil teachers.
4. During teaching and training in classes at B.Ed college as well as in practising schools, modern teaching tools and resources, training in innovative pedagogy should be provided to pupil teachers.
5. Minimum basic facilities and some stipend should be provided to pupil teachers during school internship, for developing interest and motivation.
6. Not only the mentor teachers from practising schools but school principals and B.Ed supervisors should provide feedback to pupil teachers in written format highlighting their strengths and weaknesses.

Conclusion:

The perception of pupil teachers regarding their school internship and teaching practice experience indicated that the program makes the experience stressful as the planning of lesson, evaluation of students, and other works assigned in school takes a lot of time. Lack of resources and materials in practising schools, negative attitude of school students towards pupil teachers, inappropriate time of school internship (during winter vacation board exams and term end exam of other classes) emerged as themes of challenges faced by the pupil teachers during school internship. The insight and perception of pupil teachers about their school internship experiences are very important and need action to make experience more fruitful, fulfilling and satisfying.

The suggestions emerged from the above study were-

To plan school internship in accordance with school's academic calendar, following of the program, effective supervisions, provision for funds/stipend, material support, etc. lesson plans too should be brief so that pupil teachers get sufficient time to practice teaching skills, knowledge and close interaction with students. A productive school internship will be one where it serves as a milestone for professional development.

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